

Project no.:

763959

Project acronym:

MegaRoller

Project full title:

**Developing the PTO of the first MW-level
Oscillating Wave Surge Converter**

Collaborative project

H2020-LCE-2017-RES-RIA-TwoStage

Start date of project: 2018-05-01

Duration: 36 Months (3 years)

D6.5

Data management plan

Due Project Month: M06

Due delivery date: 2018-10-31

Actual delivery date: 2018-10-24

Organisation name of lead beneficiary for this deliverable:

SINTEF Energi AS

Project co-funded by the European Commission within the Horizon 2020 Program (2014-2020)		
Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	X
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

Deliverable number:	D6.5
Deliverable short title:	Data management plan
Deliverable title:	Data management plan
Work package:	WP6.7 Data management activities
Lead author:	SINTEF / Aksetøy, Laila Økdal, with contributions from all partners

Revision Control			
Date	Revision	Author(s)	Comments
2018-10-10	1	Aksetøy, Laila Økdal	Initial version

Quality Assurance, status of deliverable		
Action	Performed by	Date
Verified (WP leader)	Raymundo E. Torres-Olguin (SINTEF)	2018-10-10
Verified (Sc Coordinator)	Tuula Maki(AWE)	2018-10-11
Approved (Coordinator)	Ilpo Honkanen(Hydroll)	2018-10-24

Table of Contents

	Page
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	6
1 INTRODUCTION AND DATA SUMMARY.....	7
1.1 Purpose of the document	7
1.2 List of definitions, acronyms and abbreviations.....	7
1.3 Structure of the document.....	8
1.4 Relationship with other deliverables	8
1.5 Summary of data	9
1.5.1 MegaRoller Sharepoint site	9
1.5.2 MegaRoller community in Zenodo	9
1.5.3 Upload instructions	10
2 FAIR DATA IN THE MEGAROLLER PROJECT	12
2.1 Findable data.....	12
2.1.1 MegaRoller community in Zenodo	12
2.1.2 Naming conventions.....	12
2.1.3 Digital Object Identifiers (DOI)	12
2.1.4 Metadata in Zenodo	12
2.2 Accessible data.....	13
2.3 Interoperable data	20
2.4 Reusable data.....	20
2.4.1 Recommended Creative Commons (CC) licences.....	20
2.4.2 Availability of the MegaRoller research data sets	20
3 ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES	21
4 DATA SECURITY	22
4.1 Active project - Data security as specified for SINTEF Sharepoint site.....	22
4.2 Repository - Data security as specified for Zenodo.....	22
5 ETHICAL ASPECTS.....	23

Table of Figures

	Page
Figure 1-1 MegaRoller research results overview	11

Table of Tables

	Page
Table 2-1 All data planned to be generated in the MegaRoller project, and their accessibility.....	14

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The scope of the MegaRoller Project is to develop and demonstrate a Power Take-Off (PTO) for wave energy converters. During the project, MegaRoller will generate, collect and reuse various types of research data.

The purpose of the MegaRoller Data Management Plan (DMP) is to contribute to good data handling, to indicate what research data the project expects to generate/collect and what can be shared with the public. The DMP gives instructions on naming conventions, metadata structure and storing of the research data set. During the 36 months of active project, a Sharepoint site will be used as the working and collaboration area for this project. All data sets will be uploaded to this site and metadata will be added. Detailed instruction on uploading research data set is given.

MegaRoller will use the Zenodo repository to comply to H2020 Open Access Mandate. The mandate applies to research data underlying publications, but beneficiaries can also voluntarily make other data set open. In MegaRoller all scientific publications and the research data set underlying will be uploaded to the MegaRoller Community in Zenodo. Other data set with dissemination level "Public" will also be uploaded to Zenodo. Each data set will be given a persistent identifier (DOI), supplied with relevant metadata and closely linked to MegaRoller grant number and project acronym. Publications and underlying research data will be linked. Creative Common licences will regulate reuse of the MegaRoller research data. Data security arrangements are defined for the Sharepoint site and Zenodo. Ethical aspects affecting data sharing have been considered.

1 INTRODUCTION AND DATA SUMMARY

1.1 Purpose of the document

The purpose of this Data Management Plan (DMP) is to contribute to good data handling during the MegaRoller project and detailing what data the project will generate, whether and how it will be exploited or made accessible for verification and re-use, and how it will be curated and preserved.

1.2 List of definitions, acronyms, and abbreviations

BibTeX	is a reference management software for formatting lists of references.
CC licence	Creative Commons licences are tools to grant copyright permissions to creative work.
CC-BY	This CC-license lets others distribute, remix, tweak, and build upon your work, even commercially, as long as they credit you for the original creation. This is the most accommodating of licenses offered. Recommended for maximum dissemination and use of licensed materials.
CC-BY-SA	This CC-license lets others remix, tweak, and build upon your work even for commercial purposes, as long as they credit you and license their new creations under the identical terms. This license is often compared to “copyleft” free and open source software licenses. All new works based on yours will carry the same license, so any derivatives will also allow commercial use.
CC-BY-NC	This CC-license lets others remix, tweak, and build upon your work non-commercially, and although their new works must also acknowledge you and be non-commercial, they don’t have to license their derivative works on the same terms.
CSL	Citation Style Language is an open XML-based standard to format citations and Bibliographies.
DMP	Data management plan.
DOI	Digital Object Identifier.
FAIR data	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-useable data
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation is an open-standard file format.
MARCXML	MARCXML is an XML schema based on the common MARC21 standards.
OAI-PMH	The Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting.
Research data	Refers to information, in particular facts or numbers, collected to be examined and considered as a basis for reasoning, discussion, or calculation. In a research context,

examples of data include statistics, results of experiments, measurements, observations resulting from fieldwork, survey results, interview recordings, and images.

- REST API** REST is an architectural style that defines a set of constraints to be used for creating web Services. API means Application Programming Interface.
- SSL/TLS** Secure Sockets Layer / Transport Layer Security are protocols offering secure communication on the internet.
- Zenodo** Zenodo is a catch-all repository that enables researchers, scientists, EU projects and institutions to share research results, make research results citable and search and reuse open research results from other projects. Zenodo is harvested by the OpenAIRE portal.

1.3 Structure of the document

This document is structured as follows:

- Section 1 is an introduction chapter describing the main purpose of the DMP and data summary.
- Section 2 describes the main principles (FAIR) for the data management in the project and how MegaRoller will comply with the H2020 Open Access Mandate.
- Section 3 describes the allocation of resources.
- Section 4 gives a detailed description of data security arrangements.
- Section 5 deals with ethical aspects connected to data management in the MegaRoller project.

The tool DMPOnline, hosted by Data Curation Centre has been used generating this document. It is based on the Horizon 2020 DMP template.

1.4 Relationship with other deliverables

The DMP is not a fixed document but evolves during the lifespan of the project. Deliverable D6.5 is the initial version of the MegaRoller Data Management Plan.

- Deliverable D6.19 Data management update, due month 18 will be a more detailed and updated version of the document.
- D6.14 Data management report, due month 36 will be the final version of this document.

This document complements the following deliverables:

- D6.1 Communication plan
- D6.3 Dissemination plan
- D7.1 Project Quality Handbook

1.5 Summary of data

The scope of the MegaRoller Project is to develop and demonstrate a Power Take-Off (PTO) for wave energy converters. MegaRoller will generate and reuse various types of data. The data will have various formats as: txt, xls, mat, mdl, pdf and others.

The size of the data will vary but will in total be moderate and should not represent any challenge regarding storage capacity or handling. A more detailed list of planned data sets and accessibility is given in Table 2-1.

1.5.1 MegaRoller Sharepoint site

All data sets in the MegaRoller project will be stored in a SINTEF Sharepoint project site. This will be the projects working and collaboration area during 36 months of active project period. Every partner will be responsible for uploading the data sets they have created/collected. All datasets will use standard Sharepoint version control.

These metadata will be provided for each data set:

- File name
- Date
- Version
- File type
- Description
- WP number
- Responsible person
- Lead
- Dissemination level

1.5.2 MegaRoller community in Zenodo

The MegaRoller project will use Zenodo to comply with H2020 Open Access mandate. All scientific publications and underlying data set will be uploaded to the MegaRoller community in Zenodo. In addition, the project will upload other data sets with dissemination level "Public" and make them open accessible via Zenodo.

1.5.3 Upload instructions

The text box below and Figure 1-1 give the upload instructions for Sharepoint and Zenodo:

Upload instructions - MegaRoller Sharepoint Site
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Please upload all MegaRoller data sets to this folder in the MegaRoller Sharepoint site:<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ 100 Research data• Use this naming convention (for details see 2.1.2):<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ <i>Descriptive text H2020_MegaRoller_DeliverableNumber_UniqueDataNumber</i>○ <i>Descriptive text H2020_MegaRoller_PublicationNumber_UniqueDataNumber</i>• Be sure to use the same file name when uploading later versions• Register mandatory metadata on your data set by adding a new item to this list:<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ MegaRoller Research Data
Upload instructions - Zenodo
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Research data underlying scientific publications/classified as "Public" should, in addition, be uploaded to the MegaRoller Community in Zenodo.<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ Create a profile in Zenodo to be able to upload files• Uploading should be done as soon as possible and at the latest on article publication. Each partner is responsible for uploading data sets created/collected by them. If needed task leader WP6.7 will supply assistance.

Figure 1-1 MegaRoller research results overview and upload instructions

1

¹ The figure is based on the graph "Open access to scientific publication and research data in the wider context of dissemination and exploitation" in [Guidelines to the Rules on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Open Access to Research Data in Horizon 2020](#)

2 FAIR DATA IN THE MEGAROLLER PROJECT

The MegaRoller project work according to the principles of **FAIR data** (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable.) The project aims to maximise access to and re-use of research data generated by the project. At the same time, there are data sets generated in this project that cannot be shared due to commercial or IPR reasons. Table 2.1 gives details on the data sets and accessibility.

2.1 Findable data

2.1.1 MegaRoller community in Zenodo

MegaRoller will use Zenodo repository as the main tool to comply with the H2020 Open Access mandate. A MegaRoller community has been established. All scientific articles/papers and public data sets will be uploaded to this community in Zenodo and enriched with standard Zenodo metadata, including Grant Number and Project Acronym. Every partner will be responsible for uploading data sets that they have created/collected and to assign relevant keywords. Zenodo provides version control and assigns DOIs to all uploaded elements.

2.1.2 Naming conventions

Data will be named using the following naming conventions:

Descriptive text H2020_MegaRoller_DeliverableNumber_UniqueDataNumber
Descriptive text H2020_MegaRoller_PublicationNumber_UniqueDataNumber

Example: RMS_simulation_H2020_MegaRoller_2.2_3

2.1.3 Digital Object Identifiers (DOI)

DOI's for all data sets will be reserved and assigned with the DOI functionality provided by Zenodo. DOI versioning will be used to assign unique identifiers to updated versions of the data records.

2.1.4 Metadata in Zenodo

Metadata associated with each published data set will by default be

- Digital Object Identifiers and version numbers
- Bibliographic information
- Keywords
- Abstract/description
- Associated project and community
- Associated publications and reports
- Grant information
- Access and licensing info
- Language

2.2 Accessible data

The H2020 Open Access Mandate aims to make research data generated by H2020 projects accessible with as few restrictions as possible, but also accept protecting of sensitive data due to commercial or security reasons.

All public data sets underlying scientific publications will be uploaded to Zenodo, and made open, free of charge. The project will, in addition, make other data sets with dissemination level "Public" open access via Zenodo. Publication and underlying data sets will be linked through persistent identifiers. Data sets with dissemination level "Confidential" will not be shared due to commercial exploitation.

Metadata including licences for individual data records as well as record collections will be harvestable using the OAI-PMH protocol by the record identifier and the collection name. Metadata is also retrievable through the public REST API. The data will be available through www.zenodo.org, and hence accessible using any web browsing application.

Information on needed software tools will be provided.

The table below provides a list of all data expected to be generated in the MegaRoller project and their planned accessibility. We recognize that this list will be more complete or can change as the project proceeds.

Table 2-1 All data planned to be generated in the MegaRoller project, and their accessibility

Task	Description/Name of data	Purpose	Format	Origin (Lead)	Class	Comments
1.1	Wave prediction at MegaRoller installation site	Specify the wave characteristics at MegaRoller installation site for power performance and load estimation		UiB	PU	Subject to approval from partners
1.2	WEC-Sim outputs. Load characterisation	Supports the evidence that the code is functional, and the results are acceptable	MATLAB files (*.mat)	CAT	CO	Subject to approval from AWE
1.3	WEC-Sim outputs. Load characterisation	Provide load and motion envelope faced by drivetrains for input to Task 1.5	MATLAB files (*.mat)	CAT	CO	Subject to approval from AWE
1.4	WEC-Sim outputs. Validation data	verification, pre-validation and validation results of the WEC numerical model	MATLAB files (*.mat)	CAT	CO	Subject to approval from AWE
1.5	List of requirements to update the design of the mechanical structure. Design of test bench	Specify the components so that they can be ordered and installed		CAT	CO	Subject to approval from AWE
1.6	Records all inspection and testing requirements relevant to the construction activities. CTI, safety and quality plan	Guide the implementation and integration of the upgraded test bench		CA/AWE/ABB/Hydman/Hydroll	CO	Subject to approval from partners

2.1	Reports, excel-sheets	Determine the charging method for the PTO	pdf/xls	Hydroll	CO	The method could be patented. After patent, it will be public but not before.
2.1	Conceptual and detailed hydraulic design	To find hydraulic components	Report (word/pdf)	AWE	CO	
2.2	electrical layout, design and select the electrical components	To find electrical components for PTO system and electric distribution	tbd	ABB	CO	Commercial reason and Security reasons
2.2	Specifications, Data for LCOE	The expected cost of the main equipment needs to be	xls	ABB	CO	Commercial exploitation
2.3	Conceptual and detailed mechanical design	Twin drive train innovation	Report (word/pdf)	AWE	CO	
2.4	Conceptual and detailed control system design	Control system design	Report (word/pdf)	AWE	CO	
2.5	Preliminary Life Cycle Assessment report and	Environmental and socio-economic acceptance of the project	pdf	WavEC	CO	Data confidentiality reasons regarding the LCA
2.5	Environmental Impact Assessment standard model	Environmental and socio-economic acceptance of the project	pdf	WavEC	PU	EIA standard model can be shared with the Public
3.1	Description of hydraulic components	Hydraulic implementation	Report		CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)
3.2	Specifications, Datasheets	Datasheets of the main components for checking more	pdf	ABB	CO	Commercial exploitation

		detail specifications of the components				
3.2	ABB manufacture, deliver and commissioning electrical components	To find electrical components for PTO system and electric distribution	tbd	ABB	CO	Commercial reason and Security reasons
3.3	Mechanical implementation	Mechanical components	Report (word/pdf)	AWE	CO	
3.4	Wave height/ MegaRoller panel movement prediction	Control system implementation	txt	AWE	CO	Public data sharing requires approval from the consortium.
3.4	Control system implementation	Control system software	Report (Word/pdf)	AWE	CO	
3.5	Handover meeting report	Hand-over to capture assembly requirements	Report (word/pdf)	AWE	CO	Report/Document
4.1	Health & safety risk assessment report		Report (word/pdf)	AWE	CO	Report/Document
4.2	CTI, safety and quality assurance plans (PTO)		Report (word/pdf)	AWE	CO	Document
4.4	Assembly instructions and order	Assembly work	Report (word/pdf)	AWE	CO	
5.2	PTO performance and power quality validation results	Validation of PTO	Report (word/pdf)	AWE	CO	

5.2	PTO performance and power quality validation results, Report	Contrast the experimental results with the simulated ones.	TXT, XLS or PDF	VTT, ABB	CO	Commercial exploitation
5.3	Validation data	Validation of PTO reliability		VTT	CO	
5.4	Final LCA report and Environmental Impact Assessment of the MegaRoller device	Evaluation of the socio-economic impacts of the project	pdf	WavEC	PU	
5.5	LCC data	Validation of PTO reliability		VTT	CO	
6.3	Innovation management plan		Report (word/pdf)	AWE	PU	Document
6.3	Innovation management report incl. IPR Registry I		Report (word/pdf)	AWE	CO	Report/Document
6.3	Innovation management report incl. IPR Registry II		Report (Word/pdf)	AWE	CO	Report/Document
6.4	Find new opportunities and potential users of the Mega Roller project technologies	To find electrical components for PTO system and electric distribution	tbd	ABB	CO	Commercial reason and Security reasons
6.5	Exploitation plan draft		Report (word/pdf)	AWE	CO	Document
6.5	Exploitation plan update I and II		Report (Word/pdf)	AWE	CO	Document

6.5	LCOE report		Report (Word/pdf)	AWE	PU	Report/Document
6.5	Business cases		Report (Word/pdf)	AWE	PU	Report/Document
6.6	Description of the existing standards and their applicability. Gap analysis matrix	Assesses the salient gaps in certification related to the specifics of the technology	pdf	CAT	PU	Useful for Technology developers considering a certification process; standardisation work groups; certification bodies
7.1	Project Quality Handbook		Report (Word/pdf)	AWE	CO	Document
7.1	Project management plan		Report (Word/pdf)	AWE	CO	Document
7.1	Project management report I and II		Report (Word/pdf)	AWE	CO	Report/Document
7.1	Final (Public) Report		Report (Word/pdf)	AWE	PU	Report/Document
8.1	Project coordination plan		Report		CO	Document Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)
8.2	Project coordination update		Report		CO	Document Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

8.3	Project coordination report		Report		CO	Document Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)
-----	-----------------------------	--	--------	--	----	--

2.3 Interoperable data

Zenodo uses JSON schema as internal representation of metadata and offers export to other formats such as Dublin Core, MARCXML, BibTeX, CSL, DataCite and export to Mendeley. The data record metadata will utilise the vocabularies applied by Zenodo. For certain terms, these refer to open, external vocabularies, e.g.: license (Open Definition), funders (FundRef) and grants (OpenAIRE). Reference to any external metadata is done with a resolvable URL.

2.4 Reusable data

The MegaRoller project will enable third parties to access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate (free of charge for any user) all public data sets, and regulate this by using Creative Commons Licences.

2.4.1 Recommended Creative Commons (CC) licences

Creative Commons licences are a tool to grant copyright permissions to creative work. As a default, the CC-BY-SA license will be applied for public MegaRoller data. This license lets others remix, tweak, and build upon your work even for commercial purposes, as long as they credit you and license their new creations under the identical terms. This license is often compared to “copyleft” free and open source software licenses. All new works based on yours will carry the same license, so any derivatives will also allow commercial use. This does not preclude the use of less restrictive licenses as CC-BY or more restrictive licenses as CC BY-NC not allowing commercial usage. This will be assessed in each case.

2.4.2 Availability of the MegaRoller research data sets

For data published in scientific journals, the underlying data will be made available no later than by journal publication. The data will be linked to the publication. Data associated with public deliverables will be shared once the deliverable has been approved by the EC.

Open data can be reused in accordance with the Creative Commons licences. Data classified as confidential will as default not be reusable due to commercial exploitation.

The public data will remain reusable via Zenodo for at least 20 years. This is currently the lifetime of the host laboratory CERN. In cases, Zenodo is phased out their policy is to transfer data/metadata to other appropriate repositories.

The process of classifying research outputs from MegaRoller is described in D7.1 Project Quality Handbook.

3 ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

MegaRoller uses standard tools and a free of charge repository. The costs of data management activities are limited to project management costs and will be covered by the project grants.

(Resources needed to support reuse of data after active project period will be solved from case to case).

SINTEF Energi AS is the lead for MegaRoller WP 6 Dissemination, Standardization & Exploitation, and for task 6.7 Data management activities. Task leader is Laila Økdal Aksetøy.

4 DATA SECURITY

In this chapter, the security issues of the research data infrastructure in the MegaRoller project are explained.

4.1 Active project - Data security as specified for SINTEF Sharepoint site.

SINTEF Sharepoint is the working/collaboration area for the MegaRoller project. A dedicated folder for research data sets has been established.

The MegaRoller Sharepoint site has these security settings:

- Access level: Restricted to persons (project members only)
- Encryption with SSL/TLS protects data transfer between partners and SINTEF Sharepoint site
- Threat management, security monitoring, and file-/data integrity prevents or registers possible manipulation of data

Documents and elements in SINTEF Sharepoint sites are stored in Microsoft's cloud solutions - in Ireland and the Netherlands. There is no use of data centres in the US or outside EU/EEA (Norway, Iceland or Switzerland).

Nightly back-ups are handled by SINTEF's IT operations contractor. All project data will be stored for 10 years according to SINTEF ICT policy.

4.2 Repository - Data security as specified for Zenodo

The MegaRoller project has chosen Zenodo as its repository. All scientific publications, public deliverables, and public research data set will be uploaded to the MegaRoller community in Zenodo and made open accessible for everyone.

These are the security settings for Zenodo:

- Versions: Data files are versioned. Records are not versioned. The uploaded data is archived as a Submission Information Package. Derivatives of data files are generated, but original content is never modified. Records can be retracted from public view; however, the data files and record are preserved.
- Replicas: All data files are stored in CERN Data Centres, primarily Geneva, with replicas in Budapest. Data files are kept in multiple replicas in a distributed file system, which is backed up to tape on a nightly basis.
- Retention period: Items will be retained for the lifetime of the repository. This is currently the lifetime of the host laboratory CERN, which currently has an experimental programme defined for the next 20 years at least.
- Functional preservation: Zenodo makes no promises of usability and understandability of deposited objects over time.
- File preservation: Data files and metadata are backed up nightly and replicated into multiple copies in the online system.
- Fixity and authenticity: All data files are stored along with an MD5 checksum of the file content. Files are regularly checked against their checksums to assure that file content remains constant.
- Succession plans: In case of closure of the repository, best efforts will be made to integrate all content into suitable alternative institutional and/or subject based repositories.

5 ETHICAL ASPECTS

Currently, no ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing have been identified. Ethical aspects connected to research data generated by the project will be considered as the work proceeds.